

LEXICAL FEATURES OF MEDIA LANGUAGE ON THE MATERIAL OF UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Annotation: *Today, mass information delivery, influencing people, and sharing news through the media are becoming widespread. In Uzbek content also, the electronic press has different stylistic features, this article presents the main purpose of the media language, its lexical-stylistic features in the Uzbek press and their examples.*

Keywords: *journalism, media languages, colloquial language, Journalistic resources, Discourse Markers.*

The predominance of the anthropocentric paradigm led to the manifestation of the interest of scholars in the study of media language in the second half of the 20th century. Mass media texts are essentially texts prepared by journalists or press officers for readers/listeners/spectators and are the language layer that most quickly reflects the language processes taking place. The peculiarity of the development of the mass media "indicates the ability of any media to play a social role in culture, to influence the audience" and, accordingly, it is possible not only to inform, but also to manipulate society.

At the beginning of the 21st century, the mass media has become the most powerful means of influencing the public consciousness: the function of persuasion begins to replace the rest of the functions of language, and the mass media become tools of mass influence. It is known that the control of people's minds and their influence on their psychological and emotional states has been felt through the information published in the press.

Considering the characteristics of modern mass media language as the main object of mediallynguistics, he defined the following tasks: we will consider the historiography of the issue of studying the mass media language, its main features and pragmalinguistic features of media texts.

Taking into account the different opinions of researchers, we believe that media text is a special type of dialogical text that works in mass communication discourse, has an informative and pragmatic orientation, addresses social, cultural, national, political and other powers. The main features of modern media texts include

openness, syncretism of style and genre, expressiveness, intertextual relations, polycode, creativity, potential polysemanticism, reference to precedent.

It should be noted that in the last decade the Internet has become the main media space, in its space the language is updated and new types of media texts have begun to develop. Almost all leading publications have their own Internet versions, and broadcasts of global TV channels and radio companies are carried out online in parallel. Characteristics such as efficiency, multimedia, interactivity, continuous feedback allow scholars to separate Internet media into separate media in the media system. These factors determine the interest of modern linguists in studying the linguistic features of Internet texts. As N. B. Mechkovskaya noted, in the 21st century, television will cease to be a dominant means of information: it will be replaced by the interactive multimedia of the Internet, which will become the information environment of every person's existence¹.

If at the end of the 20th century, scientists mainly studied the stylistic features of the language of mass media, today active processes are taking place at almost all levels of the language. At the same time, linguistic features of media texts are studied taking into account discursive-cognitive features. In our opinion, mediallynguistics is actively developing, as well as new directions of modern linguistics (psycholinguistics, cognitive linguistics, pragmalinguistics, linguoculturology, etc.), within which comprehensive study of media language is carried out. With its special object of research (media-text / media-discourse), tasks, developing terminological apparatus, special methodology, mediallynguistics becomes one of the current directions of modern language study within the framework of anthropocentrism. Sharing the opinion of T. G. Dobrosklonskaya, we believe that the subject of mediallynguistics is the study of the functioning of language in the field of mass communication, and its main theoretical component is a special concept of media text and media discourse².

Depending on the objectives, communication instruments, text kinds, and unique characteristics of media languages in Uzbek, English, Russian, and other languages, the lexical characteristics of the language may vary. Utilising these characteristics guarantees that media languages are among the primary means of conveying objectives, efficiently disseminating information, instructing, directing, and enhancing education.

We'll concentrate on Uzbek instances of lexical elements in media language below:

¹ Annenkova I. V. Media discourse of the XXI century. Linguophilosophical aspect of the language of mass media - Moscow: MSU, 2011. - 392 p

² Antonova L. V. Media texts in modern mass communication: St. Petersburg State University, 2012. - pp. 74-80.

1. Language used in political news in media texts:

- Daniyaning markaziy *soʻl Sotsialistik-demokratik partiyasi* rahbari Mette Frederiksen 2019-yildan beri *bosh vazir* lavozimida ishlab kelmoqda. U *Yevropa Ittifoqi* gʻoyasini keng targʻib qilish hamda milliy qadriyatlarni chuqur himoya qilish borasidagi dasturi bilan tanilgan.³

-*Huquq-tartibot idoralari* xodimlari tomonidan oʻtkazilgan *tezkor tadbir* davomida U.T. ushbu oliygohda tahsil oluvchi mahalliy fuqarodan 4 ta fanning yakuniy test imtihonlaridan oʻtkazib berish uchun **2 000 AQSh dollari talab qilganligi** aniqlanib, oldindan kelishilgan **1.500 AQSh dollari** miqdoridagi pul mablagʻlarini olayotgan vaqtida *ashyoviy dalillar* bilan *qoʻlga olindi*.

Hozirda holat yuzasidan *Oʻzbekiston Respublikasi JKning tegishli moddalari* bilan *jinoyat ishi* qoʻzgʻatish rejalashtirilib, *surishtiruv harakatlari* olib borilmoqda.⁴

2. Language used in economic news in media texts:

-Oʻzbekistonning oltin-valyuta zaxiralari bir oyda 1,5 mlrd dollarga oshdi Xorijiy valyutadagi aktivlar miqdori 9,26 milliard dollarga yetgan.⁵

3. Language used in cultural news in media texts:

- Shavkat Mirziyoyev Turkiya Respublikasi *nishoni* bilan *taqdirlandi*. Mazkur *oliy mukofot* Turkiya bilan doʻstona munosabatlarni rivojlantirishga katta hissa qoʻshgan *davlat arboblari*ga beriladi.⁶

-2 iyun kuni Toshkentda “Peshqadam karvoni” *loyihasining* 2 yillik *sarhisob tadbiri* boʻlib oʻtdi. Tadbirda ustozlar, yozuvchilar, *matbuot xodimlari*, *loyiha aʼzolari* va boshqa mehmonlar *ishtirok etishdi*.⁷

4. Language used in medical news in media texts:

- Kuchli issiq sabab *tana* oʻzini sovutishga harakat qilib *zoʻriqadi* va natijada *yurak xuruji* kabi *xavfli holatlar* sodir boʻladi. Statistika koʻra, birgina AQShning oʻzida yiliga 700 dan oshiq kishi *issiq urishi* sabab *vafot etadi*.⁸

5. Language used in medical news during the period of covid-19:

-*Kasallikning ortishi, oʻlim holatining koʻpayishi karantin talablarini* kuchaytirishni taqozo etadimi? *Immunolog-infeksionist* Aziza Xoʻjaeva va *virusolog* Dildora Sekler javob berishadi.⁹

These examples are provided to illustrate lexical elements in media languages might vary based on the text's intended audience and mode of communication.

³ <https://daryo.uz/le2azXY8>

⁴ <https://darakchi.uz/uz/186133>

⁵ <https://daryo.uz/IUMcL4M3>

⁶ <https://kun.uz/34884584>

⁷ <https://kun.uz/35556106>

⁸ <https://kun.uz/72588984>

⁹ <https://t.me/darakchi/55042>

The lexical characteristics of media languages that the Uzbek electronic press represents are as followings:

Language of application: Numerous application languages are employed in the Uzbek electronic press format. Uzbek instructors, academics, and journalists can debate societal issues and the Uzbek language in articles, news, and other kinds of resources. For example,

-“*Shifokor Muazzam Ibrohimova ham bog‘chalardagi ovqatlanish tizimi og‘ir ahvolda ekanini aytdi. Unga ko‘ra, bog‘chalardagi sifatsiz taomlar 7 yoshgacha bo‘lgan bolalarning oshqozon-ichak, ovqat allergiyalari va onkologik kasalliklarga chalinishini ko‘paytirgan*”.¹⁰

Speech: The Uzbek electronic press, which represents media languages, typically uses appropriate Uzbek speech patterns. Most languages have natural, formal, and scientific vocabulary, but popular words and specific phrases in the Uzbek language are often used:

-“O‘zbekiston bozorlari yangi piyoz bilan to‘lgan. Qator viloyatlarda yetishtirilgan bahorgi piyoz hosili dalalarda qolib ketmoqda. Xo‘sh, bunga sabab nima? Dehqonlarning haddan tashqari ko‘p piyoz ekkanimi yoki ichki bozor ehtiyojidan ortgan piyozning eksporti yaxshi yo‘lga qo‘yilmaganimi?”¹¹

Words and phrases: Only words and expressions found in the Uzbek language are used by Uzbek electronic press outlets. Journalists and authors from Uzbekistan do this to illustrate how the language differs from other languages¹².

For example, “*Ammo, hozirgina noxush xabar eshitdim. Mirpo‘lat akamizni berib qo‘yibmiz. Muhtaram do‘stlar. Joylari jannatdan bo‘lsin. Tilla inson edilar*.”¹³

The followinga are also the lexical characteristics of the Uzbek media language:

1. News Language:

-“According to the newest information, an arrangement for peace has been achieved among the two nations.”

- “The shocking news just in: an immense tremor has hit the area.”

- “In a private conversation, the legislator divulged his upcoming plans.”

2. Brief and Straightforward Wording:

- “Look out for a 10-minute rundown of today's biggest stories.”

- “Our programme attempts to deliver rapid and precise data to our viewers.”-

“Let's get right to the essence and address the primary issues.”

¹⁰ <https://t.me/kunuz/76496>

¹¹ <https://kun.uz/15525017>

¹² Toshaliyev I. "Modern Uzbek language methodology", 2001.

¹³ <https://kun.uz/news/2018/02/22>

3. Markers of Discourse:

- "Additionally, the research indicates that current regulations need to be modified."
- "On the other hand, certain specialists contend the circumstance is more convoluted than it appears."
- "In summary, it is apparent that the financial sector has been seriously impacted by lately occurring reforms.¹⁴"

4. Opinion and Analysis Expression:

- "The government's decision is strongly criticised by the editorial column."
- "Researchers anticipate that the proposed legislation will have a substantial influence on the economy."
- "the views on the subject fluctuate with several welcoming the attempt while another maintain dubious."

However, another problem in this field is that media materials do not have their own classification according to genres. In the existing literature of Uzbek linguistics and journalism, they are generally listed in different quantities. The division of newspaper materials into groups according to genres is still neglected.¹⁵

Based on the wide possibilities of the modern information system, it can be said that it is necessary to create a management mechanism for obtaining, storing, using and distributing information in Uzbekistan from the point of view of common interest and common development, as well as a deep understanding of its essence and elements. Based on this vital need, we consider it necessary to apply the following methods of creating a system of ensuring national security in the information field:

First, the sociological direction. In the process of receiving and distributing information, based on the role of information of the development of society as a social reality, it is necessary to study the level of social thinking and its trends, the directions of social consciousness that are formed in society. Different layers of the population, views, professional and other social it is necessary to clarify the way of thinking based on the circumstances.

Second, the statistical direction. In a multi-ethnic country, especially in Uzbekistan, where more than 130 nationalities and peoples live, about 20 religious denominations are active, inter-ethnic and inter-religious conflicts can arise under the influence of various political interests and destructive ideas. to study the sources, to have an accurate account in this regard - to have analytical solutions to the books.

¹⁴ Medialinguistics issue 2(5). <http://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=22653329>

¹⁵ Saodat Saidnazarova. Publisistik uslub (gazeta tili)ning lingvistik xususiyatlari. Medialingvistika, lingvodidaktika va madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya: nazariya va amaliyot – 2023, pp. 80-87.

Third, political conflictology and political psychology. At a time when information is becoming a psychological threat, in a situation where various destructive ideas have their influence on the human mind and thinking, it is necessary to study the sources of political conflicts, to determine the factors, and to determine the political views and mentality. , socio-political and psychological should be studied consistently¹⁶.

Fourth, logical systemic and functional analysis. The information system, in particular, the psychological impact of information, should be evaluated as an important part of the information policy system and tool. It is necessary to approach reality in this way and draw scientific-analytical theoretical and practical conclusions. Social opinion formed under the influence of information flow in a dense information society should be consistently studied from the point of view of science.

Fifth, the priority of the idea of national independence in the information system. In the process of choosing a "product" from the information base of any citizen, ensuring priority of ideological immunity in his heart, spirit, mood, character, behavior and attitude as a consequence of all this. Of course, during the 32 years of Uzbekistan's independence, serious changes have taken place in the field of mass information communication. First of all, every citizen's right to freedom of speech and opinion, to receive and distribute information is guaranteed by the Constitution. The number of independent publications has increased dramatically. All this indicates the unique development of the national information system in the internal life of the country¹⁷.

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¹⁶ Doniyorova D. "Working with information texts and media culture". Angren, 2023

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